

Molecular Orbital Study of $[\text{BFe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$, $\text{B}=(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)$, (C_6H_7) and (C_7H_9)

D. A. BROWN*, J. P. CHESTER and N. J. FITZPATRICK

Department of Chemistry, University College, Belfield, Dublin 4, Ireland

SCCC and CNDO calculations are reported for the title series of cations and trends are noted and compared with experimental results. The staggered conformation of tricarbonyl [(1,2,3,4,5- η)-2,4-cycloheptadien-1-yl] iron(1+) is shown to be the most stable with a barrier to rotation of 1.8 eV. The deformations of (C_7H_9) and (C_6H_7) in the cations are considered. Using the SCCC method, the plane of the saturated carbons is 45° above the plane of the other carbon atoms in $[(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$, while the CNDO value is 42° . For $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$ the corresponding angles are 50° (SCCC) and 51° (CNDO).

MOLECULAR orbital calculations have been useful in studying trends within a series of related molecules. Thus the series $\text{AM}(\text{CO})_3$ [$\text{AM}=(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{Cr}$, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Mn}$, $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4)\text{Fe}$, $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Co}$ and $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ni}$] has been studied by the SCCC method considering π orbitals only in the hydrocarbon moiety¹, considering σ and π orbitals² and using the CNDO method³. In the series $[\text{BFe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$, $\text{B}=(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)$, (C_6H_7) , nucleophilic substitution has been correlated with the frontier electron density using the SCCC approach⁴. Using the INDO method, a correlation between the bond indices and the site of nucleophilic addition has been noted for tricarbonyl [(1,2,3,4,5- η)-2,4-cyclohexadien-1-yl] iron(1+)⁵. The bonding in this cation has also been discussed by Hoffmann and Hofmann⁶. In the calculations now reported the SCCC method, as used previously, was employed³. The experimental geometry of $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$ was considered⁷. The structure of $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$ was based on the analogous Mn compound⁸ and the geometry of hexacarbonyl(transazulene)dimanganese⁹ was modified to give the geometry of $[(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$.

The moiety $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ is considered to bond to a hydrocarbon by accepting electrons into the d_{xz} and d_{yz} orbitals of iron and donating them from the d_{z^2} and d_{xy} orbitals¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Experimentally it is found that $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ is a net electron donor. For example, by comparing the apparent pK_a values of para substituted anilines it was shown that $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ has an electron donating capacity similar to phenyl¹⁵. Also coordination with $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ increases the pK_a values of acids confirming the electron donating properties of tricarbonyliron^{10,16}. The aromatic nature of $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$, its ability to undergo electrophilic substitution, supports the electron donating ability of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ ¹⁷, as does the increase in stability of carbonium ions following the introduction of tricarbonyliron¹⁸. From the charges reported in Table 1, it is seen that $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$, in all cases, donates electrons to B^+ . This is particularly evident from the CNDO results

where the hydrocarbon moieties are negatively charged. It may be noted that q_B increases across

TABLE 1—CHARGES, NORMALISED MULLIKEN POPULATIONS, NORMALISED WIBERG INDICES AND CARBONYL STRETCHING FREQUENCIES

	$[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$	$[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$	$[(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$
SCCC q_B	0.292	0.314	0.325
q_{Fz}	0.595	0.613	0.627
$q_{(\sigma O)_3}$	0.113	0.073	0.048
M. P. M-C(O)	1	0.963	0.885
C-O	1	1.001	0.996
CNDO q_B	-0.153	-0.107	-0.055
q_{Fz}	0.752	0.724	0.704
$q_{(\sigma O)_3}$	0.401	0.383	0.351
WI M-C(O)	1	0.982	0.967
C-O	1	0.997	0.989
$\nu(\text{CO})^a$	2126	2116	2116
	2078	2066	2062
		1970	1970

^a Values of F. M. Hussein in cm^{-1} measured in acetonitrile.

the series for both the SCCC and CNDO calculations and $q_{(\sigma O)_3}$ decreases using both methods. However q_{Fz} increases using the SCCC method and decreases using the CNDO method across the series though the percentage differences for the iron charges are the smallest. The variations in charge distributions correlate with the carbonyl frequencies as these decrease slightly across the series. Thus in $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$ the donation of electrons from iron to B^+ is more significant than the donation to the carbonyls, relative to the later members of the series. Thus low positive charge on B and high positive charges on the carbonyl correspond to high frequencies. The metal in this model does not vary so much in charge. Therefore the model is adequate to interpret the carbonyl frequencies. In the $[\text{BFe}(\text{CO})_3]^+$ series, the average charges on B, Fe and $(\text{CO})_3$ are 0.3, 0.6 and 0.1 and for the $\text{AM}(\text{CO})_3$ the corresponding values are -0.1, 0.4

and -0.3. In the latter case, more electrons are donated to the carbonyls, corresponding to the lower frequencies in this AM(CO)₅ series. It is interesting to note that in the CNDO study of AM(CO)₅ maximum donation to A occurred in (C₆H₆)Fe(CO)₅. Qualitatively by considering LUMO energies, Pettit and coworkers noted that pentadienyl type complexes with Fe(CO)₅ have higher frequencies predicted than other complexes with butadiene or non-conjugated dienes^{1,2}.

For comparative purposes as both Mulliken population analyses and Wiberg indices are used, these values in the table were normalised to unity for [(C₆H₅)Fe(CO)₅]⁺. For the C-O values, in general, there is a decrease across the series, with the exception that there is a slight increase in going from [(C₆H₅)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ to [(C₆H₇)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ using the SCCC method. However the M-C values do not increase across the series. This is in contrast to the AM(CO)₅ series, where the M-C overlap populations decrease using both the SCCC (σ+π)³ and SCCC (π)² methods, while the C-O experimental frequencies and corresponding overlap populations increase across the series. Also the M-C(O) Wiberg indices, in general, decrease and the C-O values increase across the AM(CO)₅ series³. The field absorption mass spectra of [(C₆H₇)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ and [(C₇H₉)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ have been reported and ions corresponding to the loss of one CO from the molecular ions were detected; the spectrum of tricarbonyl(benzene)chromium consists of only the molecular ion¹⁰. These results agree with the more negative carbonyl charge in (C₆H₅)Cr(CO)₃ and its lower carbonyl frequencies.

In the figure the eclipsed and staggered conformers of [(C₇H₉)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ are defined, together with the angle α. This angle was varied and it was found, using the SCCC method, that the preferred geometry was the staggered one (α=0°), in which there is a CO group below the midpoint of the saturated C-C bond in the hydrocarbon moiety. This result is in agreement with the experimental geometry⁹. The calculated difference between the two conformers is 1.8 eV. If one or more CO groups were replaced by larger groups it might be possible to observe the rotamers of such a molecule. A variable temperature ¹³C nmr study of (C₇H₉)Fe(CO)₅(CO₂Et) showed some evidence for such rotamers by a broadening of the carbonyl shift as the temperature was lowered¹⁰. Also ³¹P nmr studies detected rotamers of [BFe(CO)₅-(EPTP)]⁺, B=(C₆H₇), (C₇H₉); x=1, 2; EPTP=4-ethyl-1-phospha-2,6,7-trioxabicyclo-[2.2.2] octane^{2,1}.

Deformations of the (C₇H₉) and (C₆H₇) ligands may be discussed. The (C₇H₉)⁺ ligand is predicted on symmetry grounds to be bent rather than planar by considering this ligand as formed from C₆H₅⁺ and C₂H₄. In the planar geometry, if the π orbitals of ethylene are in the plane of the pentadienyl carbons, there is no interaction. If all the π orbitals are parallel, the hydrogen atoms in C₆H₅⁺ and C₂H₄

would be sterically unsuitable. In the non-planar case the pentadienyl orbitals in increasing energy

Fig. 1. Staggered and eclipsed conformations of [(C₇H₉)Fe(CO)₅]⁺.

have symmetries S, A, S, A, S. In C₆H₅⁺ the lowest two are occupied. Thus the ethylene π(S) can interact with the S LUMO of C₆H₅⁺ and the A HOMO of C₂H₄ can also interact with the π*(A) of ethylene. The sum of the one electron energies of the [(C₇H₉)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ cation was calculated by the SCCC method for different values of the angle between the C₆H₅ plane and the plane of the saturated carbon atoms of the (C₇H₉)⁺ ligand. The minimum energy, calculated by least squares fit, was at 49° while the experimental value is 39°. The calculations were repeated using the CNDO method and the minimum energy was at 42°, which is closer to the experimental value. Calculations by both the SCCC and CNDO methods confirm the non-planarity of (C₆H₇) in [(C₆H₇)Fe(CO)₅]⁺. The deformation angle was calculated to be 50° using the SCCC method and 51° using the CNDO approach, while the experimental angle is 43°. Thus, both the SCCC and CNDO methods predict that the deformation in [(C₆H₇)Fe(CO)₅]⁺ is greater than in [(C₇H₉)Fe(CO)₅]⁺, in agreement with experiment.

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